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*Wind energy in the natural and social environment
Research and Innovation action (RIA)*

wimby
WIND IN MY BACKYARD

WIMBY

Wind in My Backyard: Using holistic modelling tools to advance social awareness and engagement on large wind power installations in the EU

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SHORT ABSTRACT FOR DISSEMINATION PURPOSES

Abstract | This document summarises the official project's website structure and contents, including social media handles and a style guide for consortium members to follow as project identity brief.

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LIST OF PARTNERS

No	Logo	Name	Short Name	Country
1		VRIJE UNIVERSITEIT BRUSSEL (PROJECT COORDINATOR)	VUB	Belgium
2		DANMARKS TEKNISKE UNIVERSITET	DTU	Denmark
3		INTERNATIONALES INSTITUT FÜR ANGEWANDTE SYSTEMANALYSE	IIASA	Austria
4		UNIVERSITÄT FÜR BODENKULTUR WIEN	BOKU	Austria
5	UNIVERSITY OF OSLO	UNIVERSITETET I OSLO	UiO	Norway
6		NAZKA MAPPS BVBA	NAZKA	Belgium
7		KELSO INSTITUTE EUROPE GEMEINNÜTZIGE GMBH	KIE	Germany
8		DEEP BLUE SRL	DEEP BLUE	Italy
9		UNIVERSITEIT UTRECHT	UU	Netherlands
10		POLITECNICO DI TORINO	POLITO	Italy
11		UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI DI PALERMO	UNIPA	Italy
12		APREN-ASSOCIAÇÃO PORTUGUESA DE ENERGIAS RENOVAVEIS	APREN	Portugal
13		MULTICONSULT NORGE AS	MCN	Norway

14		EIDGENOESSISCHE TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE ZÜRICH	ETH Zürich	Switzerland
15		PAUL SCHERRER INSTITUT	PSI	Switzerland
16		UNIVERSITY COLLEGE LONDON	UCL	United Kingdom

ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Description
3D	Three dimensional
GIS	Geographic information system
GW	Giga watts
NIMBY	Not in my back yard
MCSA	Multi-criteria stakeholder analysis
MW	Mega watts
SSH	Social sciences and humanities
VRE	Variable renewable energy
W3C	World wide web consortium
WCAG	Web Content Accessibility Guidelines

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In this document, the project's website and social media profiles are presented and described in detail. The website provides all the useful information about the project's objectives and planned activities. It gives an overview of the entire project, introduces the consortium partners, offers references to related projects, and represents an easy access for citizens and stakeholders to interface and receive all information related to the project. The website will be regularly updated, and it will represent the main communication and dissemination channel: news, milestones, events, planned workshops and any other announcement will be published through its news section. The project partners will support this task by sharing updates on research advancements, scientific publications, reports, public deliverables, conferences, or project results. Not only interested visitors but also the general audience will be able to read through the content, download resources, engage through the newsletter form, social media links, and have access to the General Forum. Through General Forum the audience can exchange ideas, discuss project topics and increase their understanding about renewable energy and wind power production. The Web-GIS platform which will be developed in the WIMBY project will also be linked to the website. Deep Blue (DBL), as Dissemination Leader, is responsible for the design, realisation, implementation, maintenance and update of the website and the social media pages, over the course of the project and for two years after its conclusion.

1. WIMBY WEBSITE

1.1 General information

The website will guide the user through the project's content, thanks to its designed layout and its simple and user-friendly structure. It offers a comprehensible overview of the approach, methodologies and objectives while still providing in-depth details using internal cross-links or highlighting key concepts through explanatory graphs, tables and boxes.

Firstly, extracts have been extrapolated from the project's proposal and, in some instances, rewritten for greater clarity, easy understanding and to fit the dissemination and communication objectives. Then, a framework structure and a graphical layout have been proposed to partners to better satisfy the information needs of the project's target audience. Texts have been drafted and peer reviewed by the consortium and approved by the project coordinator VUB and the scientific coordinator UU. Fonts, styles and identity, including the logo, have been chosen following the consortium preferences collected during the kick-off meeting (Brussels, 24 January 2023). The website's official address is WWW.WIMBY.EU and it is hosted on DBL servers, operated through the WordPress content management system. The website is compliant with the most recent General Data Protection Regulation – (EU) 2016/679 and the Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) (version 2.0) issued by the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) provisions.

1.2 Architecture

Figure 1 - Website architecture

2. Website pages content

2.1 Home page

2.1.1 Project in a nutshell

WIMBY is a European funded project supporting the adoption and acceptance of wind-power in the European Union. It will develop innovative tools to facilitate citizen and stakeholders' interaction, knowledge sharing, and collaborative evaluation of impacts, conflicts, synergies, and social innovation potential.

The main objective of this research is to mitigate the "Not in my backyard" (NIMBY) effect by providing practical information that all stakeholders and citizens can use for simple and comprehensible assessments, aimed at creating a common ground for participatory decision-making processes.

[READ MORE button linking to About page]

2.1.2 Concept image

[A concept image will display pilot sites across the EU]

2.1.3 Expected results

[An infographic will list objectives/results]

2.1.4 Highlighted content

[A selection of the latest/top news will appear here]

2.1.5 Newsletter form

[Form to submit/subscribe to the Newsletter]

2.2 About

2.2.1 Project overview

The WIMBY project is dedicated to increasing the use of wind power as a renewable energy source by addressing challenges that threaten its deployment, such as restrictive regulations and negative public perception.

Innovative models are used to assess wind power development impacts and potential conflicts and synergies, while guidelines are developed to increase public engagement. The project results are then translated into practical information for stakeholders to make informed decisions and shared via open-access repositories and social media.

In addition, the project will provide a Web-GIS interactive platform to enhance the accessibility and usability of the information and allow knowledge exchange from various stakeholders. The platform enables the early engagement of local stakeholders and citizens, involving them from the beginning of the project in the planning, implementation, and operating processes of wind farm deployment.

By facilitating societal engagement and support for wind power, the project aims to contribute to the decarbonisation strategy of the EU.

2.2.2 Context and challenges

Wind power is one of the fastest-growing, most mature and cost-competitive renewable energy technologies. But its deployment faces significant challenges due to a lack of knowledge of the complexity of its impacts and benefits. While wind power is seen as a promising solution to reducing carbon emissions and combating climate change, it has also met resistance from local communities.

The effect that the project seeks to counter is called NIMBY (Not In My Backyard). It describes the opposition of local communities to new developments that they feel could negatively impact their neighbourhood or community. Often, citizens are supportive of these types of projects in theory. Still, when it comes to having them built nearby, they become concerned about issues like noise, safety, and property value.

WIMBY addresses these challenges by involving citizens and stakeholders in the whole process, collecting concerns, developing easy-to-use tools, and promoting an open and transparent communication. To conduct a truly transparent and transdisciplinary research, we have involved experts such as renewable energy scientists, behavioural economists, terrestrial and marine ecologists, landscape and urban planners, environmental scientists, wind power engineers, lawyers, physicists, climate and sustainability scientists, human-computer interaction developers, human geography experts and non-profit associations.

2.2.3 Tenets of Transitional Justice in WIMBY

Transcending individual cases at the community level we pursue an approach to stakeholder engagement based on the Tenets of Transitional Justice.

[An infographic will represent the “Tenets of Transitional Justice in WIMBY”]

2.2.4 Wheel of stakeholders

Figure 2 - Preliminary list of WIMBY stakeholder ecosystem

2.2.5 Methodology

The WIMBY project will analyse how wind power affects the different communities and ecosystems across Europe thanks to a series of interactive engagement tools. Through studies and data collection, the research will develop scenarios, guidelines and models that can be applied on a large scale.

The project is a multilevel study, where the team's experience and existing studies are applied on four pilot cases. It will proceed as follows:

- 1) **Identify and assess the concerns and impacts from social, health, and environmental perspectives**, building on:
 - a) Existing data from NEWA ([link](#)) and Global Atlas of siting parameters GASP ([link](#)) and GASPOC ([link](#)) to allow computation of various technical, economic and human-relevant parameters (e.g. capacity factors, LCOE, noise etc.)
 - b) Impact assessments related with land and sea use and with the affected ecosystems.
 - c) Comparative risk assessments of impacts on society, health and sustainability.
- 2) **Identify who are the different actors affected**, thanks to:
 - a) Stakeholder mapping and MCSA, aimed at the identification of the different actors potentially benefitting from receiving incentives, social influences involved and situational socioeconomic dependencies between stakeholders. The results will be included in "prototype cases" to further explore in field studies within the four pilot sites regions, where observational studies will take place and the methodology will be refined and validated.
 - b) Stakeholder engagement in pilot sites, where the approach will be tested through workshops and guidelines and recommendations will be derived to formulate suggestions.
- 3) **Identify trade-offs and synergies between impacts to create deployment strategies** through:
 - a) Holistic system analysis, taking into consideration not only high-level techno-economic details, but also the social and ecological factors determining to what extent and in which location the wind energy can be actually deployed, weighting criteria according to expert judgement as well as stakeholder preferences towards the optimal trade-off between cost implications and minimisation of impacts.

- b) Geospatial mapping and assessment through interactive tools co-created with stakeholders and developed as a whole platform where a WebGIS, an immersive 3D simulation tool and a discussion forum will be used as empowering tools for multi-stakeholder interaction.
- c) Collection of guidelines and best practices for policy makers at the regional, national, and European level, derived from the feedback on the multi-criteria stakeholder analysis (MCSA) and the WIMBY interactive tools and laying the foundation for future participatory engagement approaches.

2.2.6 Citizen science and the role of social science and humanities

In WIMBY a tailored MCSA framework will focus on the active inclusion of citizens in all decision-making processes, offering opportunities to express needs and concerns. In parallel, they will also have a word in the definition of proper business models for financial participation, for example as energy community members. Satisfaction and acceptance questionnaires will ensure that the most important criteria, sub-criteria and parameters affecting their opinion are pointed out.

This is the reason why social science and humanities (SSH) are central to WIMBY. Their input is essential to:

- Translate research results into usable information for real-life applications.
- Investigate the acceptance of wind-power project.
- Formulate questions triggering foster positive exchange.
- Build on the skills, capacities, resources, and ideas of citizens.
- Collect feedback through appreciative inquiries.
- Properly adopt Citizen Science, collective deliberation, and co-creation approaches.

2.2.7 Objectives

[The objectives will be presented as a carousel with representative graphic icons and short accompanying texts. They will then be represented in a scheme with links to tools and resources related to those specific objectives.]

The main objectives of the project are:

S01: ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT ASSESSMENT: evaluation of the impacts on the biodiversity (terrestrial and marine fauna), estimation of wind resources availability and their consequences on land and sea use.

S02: SOCIETAL IMPACT ASSESSMENT: evaluation of how wind farms affect the local communities and addressing issues concerning governance, regulation, health, safety and landscape impacts.

S03: WIND POWER POTENTIAL DEPLOYMENT ASSESSMENT: Identification of the best areas for wind power farms deployment, while assessing through validated models how wind turbines impact on the local environment and identify methods to foster social acceptance.

S04: VALIDATION OF WIND INSTALLATION MODELING TOOLS: validation of modelling tools and development of guidelines to deliver clear overviews of the cumulative impacts of wind installations and facilitate the identification of future areas of deployment (local, regional, national and European level).

S05: WEB-GIS INTERACTIVE FORUM: implementation of a Web-GIS interactive forum where stakeholders and local communities can exchange information, ideas and inputs to support the planning of new wind turbines and wind parks.

S06: IMMERSIVE 3D ENVIRONMENT DEVELOPMENT: development of an immersive 3D environment that allows stakeholders to visualise and better understand the impacts and the trade-offs of wind energy development in their communities, to promote social awareness and early engagement of the citizens.

S07: METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION: development of a framework for wind farm planning. It will include guidelines for participatory processes based on the interaction and the opinions of the citizens exchanged on the Web-GIS forum, which will be directly accounted for in decision making. This process strengthens public awareness and knowledge, and participation procedures will be democratised.

ABOUT SCHEME

Objectives

<p>#1 OBJECTIVE ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT ASSESSMENT</p> <p>RESULT [WIMBY Environmental impact assessment] + link</p> <p>RESOURCES Link to the deliverables (D1.1 - D1.2 - D1.3 - D1.4)</p>	<p>#2 OBJECTIVE SOCIETAL IMPACT ASSESSMENT</p> <p>RESULT [WIMBY Societal impact assessment] + link</p> <p>RESOURCES Link to the deliverables (D2.2 - D2.3 - D2.6)</p>	<p>#3 OBJECTIVE WIND POWER POTENTIAL DEPLOYMENT ASSESSMENT</p> <p>RESULT [Wind power assessment tool "TopFarm 3.0"] + link</p> <p>RESOURCES Link to the deliverables (D2.1 - D2.5)</p>	<p>#4 OBJECTIVE VALIDATION OF WIND INSTALLATION MODELING TOOLS</p> <p>RESULT [WIMBY modelling tools] + link</p> <p>RESOURCES Link to the deliverables (D4.4 - D4.5)</p>
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ABOUT SCHEME

Objectives

<p>#5 OBJECTIVE WEB-GIS INTERACTIVE FORUM</p> <p>RESULT [Web-GIS platform and forum] + link</p> <p>RESOURCES Link to the deliverables (D5.1 - D3.1-4 - D6.3)</p>	<p>#6 OBJECTIVE IMMERSIVE 3D ENVIRONMENT DEVELOPMENT</p> <p>RESULT [Immersive 3D platform] + link</p> <p>RESOURCES Link to the deliverables (D5.2 - D3.1-4)</p>	<p>#7 OBJECTIVE METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION</p> <p>RESULT [Wimby methodological framework] + link</p> <p>RESOURCES Link to the deliverables (D3.1-4 - D4.2 - D4.3 - D4.5)</p>
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Figure 3 – Objectives scheme

2.2.8 Connection between tools

[A Concept image/Infographic will display the link between the tools/objectives of the project. To be developed with relevant partners' support.]

2.3 Pilot sites

2.3.1 Pilot site overview

The project will collect real-world data on four pilot sites located in Austria, Norway, Italy and Portugal to engage directly local communities and understand valuable insights into the factors that influence public attitudes towards wind power and its applications.

The selected pilot cases cover a wide range of geographical, technological and societal characteristics that ensure that the developed tools are

relevant and useful to wind power deployment and energy citizenship. Pilot sites could help to identify potential challenges and obstacles to wind power knowledge and develop more realistic strategies for promoting it.

The studies that will be carried out on a local level, can then be scaled up and be used for European-scale applications, thanks to the experiences and methodologies applied transformed into guidelines and best practices.

[Four button/images will link to each pilot site dedicated page]

[Each Pilot Site page is structured to include:

- *An introductory text*
- *A location map initially linked to online map and to the WebGIS in a later phase]*
- *4/5 pictures of the site*
- *A table with technical information about the site*
- *A box about social engagement: Leader, partners, and Key Local Stakeholders]*

2.3.2 Pantelleria – ITALY

- Pilot overview

Pantelleria is a small volcanic island located 110 km off the coast of Sicily with high potential for variable renewable energy production (VRE). The island's own electricity grid is mainly powered by diesel generators, but due to its location in one of the windiest areas in Italy, offshore wind energy would be possible.

[Location map: <https://goo.gl/maps/Uyy1n5b1M41Snv429>]

- Pilot challenges

However, there are three sites of Community Importance:

- a special protection area
- a national park
- an important bird area

They restrict the installation of the implants. Not to mention the possible opposition from the very significant tourism sector.

[Pictures of the site]

[Table with technical information about the site]

[Box about social engagement: Leader, partners and Key Local Stakeholders]

2.3.3 Rogaland – NORWAY

- Pilot overview

Karmøy is a municipality on the west coast of Norway, with a hilly, densely populated agricultural landscape, characterised as a well-preserved cultural landscape. Offshore wind farms are visible from large parts of the coastline used for recreational purposes.

A demonstration wind farm that can generate up to 85 MW of power is planned. The farm will also have a power line to connect to the grid and will use advanced ecological monitoring systems, including an AI-assisted bird tracker. This allows to study how wind turbines can affect birds and develop strategies to address this issue.

[Location map: <https://goo.gl/maps/9jG6YhoXs8cwu5VD6>]

- Pilot challenges

A planned landscape conservation area in the vicinity of the proposed wind farm is affected, as well as three existing conservation areas within a 6.0-15 km radius. Several planning options are under discussion.

The particularity of this pilot is that the wind farm development plans are already mature and serve as a test for WIMBY's tools and methodologies. The environmental impact assessment and environmental test site infrastructure allows the researchers to study how different offshore wind turbine types impact the local marine environment.

[Pictures of the site]

[Table with technical information about the site]

[Box about social engagement: Leader, partners and Key Local Stakeholders]

2.3.4 Styria – AUSTRIA

- Pilot overview

Styria is a federal state located in Austria and is characterized by its mountainous terrain, where the south-eastern parts is defined by a hilly landscape while the northern and western parts gradually give way to high

peak and glacial areas. The region is widely covered by forests and meadows and has a unique climate that combines alpine and Pannonian features, providing diverse habitats for wildlife and various species.

Styria has a significant wind power potential, particularly in its mountainous areas, where wind speeds are generally of high quality in terms of speed and consistent and are typically location at altitudes above 1,000 meters.

The region has a variety of sites suitable for the installation of wind turbines, including high altitude sites and sites in forests. With 2022 104 wind turbines with a total of 260MW were in operation. Austria set plans to install further 10GW wind power capacity by 2030 with some plans for wind farms in Styria, where the favourable areas are located on the high altitudes of the mountain ridges on both sides of the rivers Mur and Mürz, where only a few developable areas are left between large environmental protection zones.

[Location map: <https://goo.gl/maps/RcHCC58t8iLPWYKe8>]

- Pilot challenges

The implementation possibilities largely depend on the definition of priority and suitability zones, as well as exclusion zones within the federal state, which consider protection zones and wildlife. On site the local acceptance and the early involvement of stakeholders also play a role. The particularity of this pilot is that WIMBY addresses an entire region with a high wind power deployment potential and at the same time a high scenic value.

[Pictures of the site]

[Table with technical information about the site]

[Box about social engagement: Leader, partners and Key Local Stakeholders]

2.3.5 Offshore deployment – PORTUGAL

- Pilot overview

Portugal currently has 5.5 GW of installed wind power capacity, which contributes 24% of Portugal's electricity demand. By 2030, an additional 9.0 GW of onshore and 0.3 GW of offshore capacity are planned, not only through new installations but also through repowering the existing ones.

[Location map: maps: <https://goo.gl/maps/7unsFK49AJP6vDZq7>]

- Pilot challenges

The feasibility of these expansion plans is highly dependent on the communication and cooperation between stakeholders, grid operators, authorities, and local communities, to ensure low environmental impact and high public support.

The particularity of this pilot is that WIMBY addresses and enriches the Web-GIS tool through interaction with companies that are responsible for almost all the installed wind power capacity in Portugal.

[Pictures of the site]

[Table with technical information about the site]

[Box about social engagement: Leader, partners and Key Local Stakeholders]

2.4 Team

Partners logos and access to company websites

[Project Coordinator Logo (VUB)]

[Scientific Coordinator Logo (UU)]

[Partners Logos, Websites and Country of Origin]

[Advisory Board members]

[[Sister projects](#) (project logos with link and short abstract)]

2.5 Web-GIS and Forum

2.5.1 Web-GIS tools description, features and use

A Web-GIS platform is a tool that combines web technologies with geographic information systems (GIS) to provide interactive maps and other visualisations on the internet. It allows users to access and analyse geospatial data from various sources and to create customised maps and applications that can be shared with others.

Web-GIS platforms are useful for a wide range of applications: they allow to combine environmental, society, health data and much more. They can help users make informed decisions, communicate complex spatial information to stakeholders, promote transparency and citizen collaboration.

The WIMBY project is developing a web-GIS platform to provide interactive maps and other visualisations to help stakeholders understand the impacts, conflicts, and potentials of wind power development in the selected area.

The Web-GIS is tailored to all kind of users, expert and not-experts to explore, assess and evaluate for themselves the implications of wind farm development at local, regional, national and international level. In both cases, the interaction with the Web-GIS is facilitated using a minimalistic design and intuitive operation, to facilitate the user experience and make the tool affordable for everyone.

[Web-GIS link]

[Representative picture]

2.5.2 General Forum description, features, use and login link

WIMBY will also develop an interactive forum where regulators, industry experts, and local communities can exchange information and provide ideas to support the planning of new wind turbines and parks. A space, where, also, project's results and outcomes can be saved, shared, and commented on.

This forum will allow stakeholders to see the different environmental, economic, and social aspects to consider when developing wind power projects. The platform will also help identify the best areas for deploying wind turbines based on validated models and holistic assessment metrics, such as the evaluation of the environmental impact of wind turbines throughout their lifecycle, the evaluation of the social and economic benefits and costs of wind energy development, the evaluation of various criteria (environmental, economic, social...), etc.

By combining the interactive forum with the WEB-GIS platform, the identification of future areas for wind power deployment will be easier, more affordable and based on people participation.

[Login link – when available]

[Representative picture]

2.6 Resources

2.6.1 Resources overview

Find here all useful materials developed by WIMBY project.

Contents will be free to download. Following descriptions will be used as abstracts when related results will be available.

2.6.2 Tools

Description of the tools.

2.6.3 Deliverables

List of the published deliverables.

2.6.4 Press releases

List of the published press releases.

2.6.5 Scientific publications

Links to the site where the scientific articles have been published.

2.6.6 Infographics and media

Downloadable graphic materials.

2.7 News and Events

Latest news in grid visualisation

2.8 Contacts

[Form to submit inquiries and contact the project team, plus additional relevant contacts]

2.9 Standard pages

Set of standard pages and features normally accessed through the header or footer bar:

- Privacy policy
- Terms of use
- Credits
- Social media links
- Search bar

3. Social Media pages

[Access to social media profiles will be available on the website footer and an access plugin will also allow sharing project news through built-in sharing buttons provided beside.]

3.1 LinkedIn

WIMBY project LinkedIn account has been created as a non-profit company profile at the following link:

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/wimby-wind-in-my-backyard/about/>

3.2 Twitter

WIMBY project Twitter account has been created at the following link:

https://twitter.com/WIMBY_project

4. NEXT STEPS

The project website is a continuously growing content manager, therefore updates to the abovementioned contents and changes in its initial structure are still possible and will be done according to communication and dissemination needs over time.

ANNEX 1

Visual identity

In this Annex the project visual identity is provided, as a reference for partners to ensure a homogeneous style in all communication and dissemination products and activities. It contains:

- Different applications of the project logos
- Decorative elements
- Font styles
- Colour palette

WIMBY
STYLEGUIDE

Figure 4 - Wimby decorative element

Figure 5 - Logo application on dark backgrounds

HORIZONTAL

Figure 6 - Logo in horizontal version, coloured and black & white

Figure 7 – Logo in vertical version, coloured and black & white

TYPOGRAPHY

COMFORTAA
Titles

**LOREM
IPSUM**

Poppins
Texts

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed diam nonummy nibh euismod tincidunt ut laoreet dolore magna aliquam erat volutpat. Ut wisi enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrud exerci tation ullamcorper suscipit lobortis nisl ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat. Duis autem vel eum iriure dolor in hendrerit in vulputate velit esse molestie consequat, vel illum dolore eu feugiat nulla facilisis at vero eros et accumsan et justo odio dignissim qui blandit praesent luptatum zzril delenit augue dui dolore te feugait nulla facilisi.

WIMBY - STYLEGUIDE

5

Figure 8 – project font styles

COLOR PALETTE

WIMBY - STYLEGUIDE

6

Figure 9 – project colour palette